

INTERNAL DIMENSIONS OF WORKPLACE DIVERSITY AND MULTINATIONAL CORPORATIONS SUSTAINABILITY IN NIGERIA

¹*OLU-OGUNLEYE, ITUNU, ¹AKINBODE, JAMES O. and ²OGUNLEYE, OLUWOLE

¹Department of Industrial Relations & Personnel Management, Bowen University, Iwo, Osun State, Nigeria.

*Corresponding Author Email: itunu.olu-ogunleye@bowen.edu.ng

²Department of Social Development, Rufus Giwa Polytechnic, Owo, Ondo State, Nigeria.

Abstract

The study examined internal dimensions of workplace diversity and sustainability of selected multinational corporations in Nigeria. The study sought to investigate the extent to which internal dimensions of workplace diversity (age, gender, ethnicity) contribute to the sustainability of Multinational corporations in Nigeria. This study adopted a descriptive survey research design. A sample of 255 respondents from two leading manufacturing multinational corporations in Nigeria was employed. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyse the data in the study. The result showed that internal dimensions of workplace diversity have a significant relationship to sustainability. Workplace diversity is unavoidable in Nigerian manufacturing MNCs because most workers have different social and economic statuses, which induces their actions or thinking to differ from others, which must be managed for the organisation to be effective. When managed properly, the organisation will interact with people from various cultures, ethnic groups, age race, gender and also diverse customers, which will aid in the development of new attitudes, ideas, skills, processes, and solutions to difficult problems. The study recommends that MNCs should employ individuals from various internal dimensions in other to achieve organizational sustainability.

Keywords: Age, Ethnicity, Gender, Internal dimensions, Workplace diversity, Sustainability

Introduction

Businesses of any kind are floated to continuously meet the needs of different stakeholders now and in the future without causing any harm irrespective of the growing contentions within the business or external to it (Mensah, 2019). This philosophy explains why business ideas have shifted solely from pursuing economic objectives such as profit to including people (social), and planet (environmental) objectives. These business objectives have been jointly described as business sustainability, a concept that has attracted discourse in the recent past among business managers, industrialists, and academia. Amos and Uniamikogbo (2016) defines sustainability as an integrative conceptual framework describing an attractive, wholesome, and vibrant equilibrium among natural and human systems, a set of regulations, attitudes, and standards that will safeguard the diverse nature of the earth's ecosystems, promote economic vigour and possibility, as well as provide a high quality of life for people, and an image of a future that anyone would want to live in.

MNCs in particular, generate robust performance to the three pillars of sustainability when particularly in comparison to other organisations, such as their size and magnitude in the international business landscape, availability of investment capital and resources, the transfer of advanced technology, and the capacity to provide goods and services to people living in

rural or remote areas. The triple bottom line of sustainability includes economic or financial issues, environmental preservation, and societal and individual well-being. This means boosting economic and social well-being while staying within nature's carrying capacity for environmental effects. The triple bottom line is achieved through sustainability (social, economic, environmental). It also refers to an organisation's efforts to manage the market and social impact on the environment, society, and economy, rather than focusing solely on profit (Durst & Zieba, 2020).

Tamunomiebi and Chika (2020) articulated that the difference and resemblance that exists among employees in terms of age, gender, race, culture, religion, and nation is referred to as workplace diversity. Khan and Jabeen (2019) remark that business organisations should have the option to draw in, retain, advance, and develop a high-potential workforce from different cultures, races, age groups, and gender, to prosper in the global economy, people of all ethnic backgrounds must work together. Furthermore, the world of work is becoming more diverse than ever before as a result of globalisation (Inegbedion et al, 2020), individuals no longer work, and reside in their immediate environment alone there is now a great interaction with the global environment at large.

Akinnusi et al (2017), Dewua, (2019), and Tamunomiebi and John-Eke, (2020) used personality, internal dimension, external dimension, and organisational dimension to divide the dimensions of workplace diversity into four categories. Internal dimensions are traits that have a major impact on people's views, expectations, and attitudes toward others, such as age, gender, ethnicity, race, culture, and physical ability

The category of business that seems to be exposed to high chances of extinction if sustainability is not given a top priority is the multinationals. Joseph et al. (2019) opined that MNCs is a business entity that operates in different countries. Since Nigeria's workplace is overflowing with diverse people, the relevance of workplace diversity has become a very visible attraction to MNCs in various countries, including Nigeria (Idam, 2020). The manufacturing sector of any economy overall is presumed to be the driving force of growth and an impetus for sustainable businesses, economic change, and national development (Afolabi & Laseinde, 2019; Banjoko et al., 2012). Oyati (2010) opined growth in assembling has critical beneficial outcomes on work creation, supported expansions, and sustained increase in per capita pay, technology advancement, and reception, he also noted that the development pace of the manufacturing sector in a nation reflects its financial prospect.

Objective of the Study

The objective of the study is to investigate the contributions of internal dimensions of workplace diversity to the sustainability of selected manufacturing multinational corporations

Hypothesis

Internal dimensions of workplace diversity do not significantly contribute to the sustainability of selected manufacturing multinational corporations

Literature Review

Diversity means the variety, differences, and variety of qualities, both noticeable and imperceptible, which establish a marvel in both the inanimate and animate worlds. (Akinnusi et al. 2017). Inegbedion et al. (2020) define diversity as the differences in employees as a result of various backgrounds they belong to, these backgrounds include gender, age, color, ethnicity, physical ability, etc. According to Akinnusi et al. (2017), other aspects of diversity include lifestyle, tenure, position in the organization, functional specialty or geographical location. Workplace diversity is concerned with the variations and similarities that individuals contribute to an organization. Diversity can be seen as a quite bit of differences and similarities that exist among people, diversity includes a large number of human characteristics and qualities which could be race, sexual orientation, or ethnicity (Idam, 2020). Szymanska and Aldighieri (2017) define diversity as a collection of different mixture of individuals with differences and similarities that includes individual and organization qualities, values, perceptions, beliefs, and practices.

Workplace Diversity is simply how diverse the workforce is in terms of age, culture, background race, etc. (Preeti et al., 2014). According to Tamunomiebi and Chika (2020), workplace diversity refers to the differences and similarities that exist amongst employees in terms of age, gender, ethnicity, culture, religion, nationality, and so on. Workplace diversity also includes disparities that occur inside a company's departments, divisions, and subsidiaries that are based in various areas or countries. Diversity management implies recognizing individuals' differences and acknowledging that these differences are essential. It requires satisfactory management practices by avoiding discrimination. The bedrock of workplace diversity lies in the premise of individuality within a workplace, recognizing that each individual can bring something unique to the business (Betchoo, 2015).

Betchoo, (2015) and Preeti et al. (2014) identified some advantages of diversity in the workplace.

- i. **Increased Productivity:** Making diversity a priority in the workplace helps to optimize productivity; the unique ideas and enthusiasm of a varied team provide good results. Diversity in the workplace offers employees, regardless of their cultural background, a sense of belonging to the organization by remaining loyal and industrious, which helps to boost the organization's productivity and profit.
- ii. **Remove Bias and Discrimination:** Diversity in the workplace destroys any societal bias. Employees see themselves as one, with no discrimination on any ground.
- iii. **Improve Teamwork:** A diverse team makes better judgments, generates fresh ideas, and offers multiple solutions to problems. An individual juggling many tasks cannot accomplish at the same rate as a group; so, each worker contributes different ideas and perspectives during critical thinking to arrive at the best solution in the shortest time. When compared to individuals who make business decisions, a diverse group may make better decisions and address a variety of difficulties. Because of their distinct and diversified traits, they can provide more advantages to the workplace.

- iv. **Increased Employee Engagement and Involvement:** when different individuals come together, they tend to learn and grow more from what they see or like from others. Workers perform better in the workplace when they believe they can mix effectively, connect, be involved, and be included, and this leads to enhanced worker participation and involvement at various points across the business.
- v. **Opportunities for self-improvement and growth:** Workplace diversity provides opportunities for employees' self-improvement and growth. When employees are exposed to diverse cultures, ideas, and viewpoints, it may assist each individual to learn new things and cognitively reach out and have a clear understanding of their role in the global context, and therefore their immediate surroundings.
- vi. **Creativity and Invention:** A diverse workplace has a better probability of innovation as a consequence of combining different thinking ideas, and viewpoints, and coming up with a whole new concept or innovation. A diversified workforce also results in unique and inventive ideas at the right time.
- vii. **Effective Communication:** diversity in the workplace can immensely strengthen an organization's relationship with stakeholders by making communication effective.

Internal Dimensions of Workplace Diversity

Internal dimension of diversity is critical in developing self and self-identity, early socialization, and establishing the centre of various personalities, characteristics and identities (Hall, 2011). Philip, (2019) sees internal dimensions as those unique qualities that are allotted to a person at birth or through other artificial ways. These dimensions include age, gender, race, ethnicity, sexual Orientation physical ability etc. These, on the other hand, include aspects of diversity over which individuals have little control (though physical ability can change after some time because of decisions we make to be dynamic or not, or in instances of disease or mishaps). These elements include the first things we encounter in a long time, such as race or sexual orientation, and on which we base countless assumptions and judgments (Chin & Trimble, 2020)

I. Age Diversity

An age-diverse organisation is one in which employees of all ages are employed and valued in the workplace. (Idam, 2020). Age diversity refers to the distribution of age differences among employees in an organisation, and it can be conceptualised in terms of their division of responsibilities, work experience, or special services they provide. The positive and negative effects of age diversity in the workplace are determined by the representatives and the organization's work arrangement. When employees of various ages work together, it creates a synergy of inspiration, information flow, an opportunity for progression planning, inventiveness, and improved navigation (Amaram, 2007). Meanwhile, if age diversity is not managed properly, it can lead to miscommunication, passionate debates, power struggles, workplace issues, and the strength of one group(s) over another, all of which can lead to high employee turnover.

According to Flanagan, (2020) the presence of different generational classes in today's workplace has increased openness to how such a mix can be used to boost employee engagement and business sustainability. The point is that if workers from a certain age group follow through on this worldview, it could give one group an advantage over another. People who are related to a specific group can, in any case, have interests and inclinations toward people in another group, even if they have no prior social relationship with those individuals. This could be a substitute impact on age variety as representatives from a particular age gathering may continually want to relate to their age bunch accepting to have comparable interests, objectives, and convictions in any event, when the other gathering ought to be recognized.

Age is likewise something other than a number. It is a striking social signifier that gives enrolment in a specific age gathering and companion. Age likewise influences people and designs society through the pessimistic power of ageism, characterized as bias, generalizing, or segregation based on age or saw age (Boni-Saenz, 2021). Age structures both individual personality and social association in incredible ways. Nonetheless, age converges with other significant classifications like race, sex, and class to create remarkable people with various interests and mindsets. Furthermore, these various parts of personality can meet in manners that produce extraordinary encounters and types of disadvantages. It is thusly basic to take care of these multifaceted impacts when considering age and the age variety of different cultural organizations.

Past studies express that older employees are more in danger than more younger employees however researchers too do not verify this result (Idam, 2020). Older established employees might confront trouble in performing various tasks relying upon the expected set of responsibilities which could postpone hierarchical yield. More youthful employees face bad introductions likewise as others will generally portray them to be less reliable, show less dedication to the brand, and are depicted as occupation containers. Suggestions on correspondence cost might emerge in the bid of expanding age diversity as exploration expresses that correspondence and foundation of social connections between irrelevant employees consequently draw in greater expenses than inside comparative workers (Harrison et al., 2002). Past studies show that age separation influences all age bunches regardless of the classification. More seasoned workers will more often than not feel dismissed, minimized and accept they are denied advancement openings while more youthful representatives accept they are of less significance because of their absence of involvement (Ellemers et al., 1988). Accordingly, all employees should get a handle on the positive effect of old enough diversity and hold fast to the administration's way of rehearsing age diversity. Therefore, organisations need to have a blend of all generations, to gain the reward of different multi-generational employees having a young extravagance and mature employees with adequate knowledge and experience (Muthoni, 2017).

II. Gender Diversity

Gender diversity, according to Cedric (2009) is defined as the possibility of the unmistakable capacities and potential outcomes of male and female representatives as equal creatures.

Gender diversity in the workplace refers to the proportion of male and female employees, which can have an impact on how employees communicate and collaborate, as well as employee commitment within the organization. In the last two decades, studies have shown that the female gender possesses a basic, unseen reservoir of human resources. With the foundation of data innovation and updating of instructive infrastructural offices, continuously qualified women are meandering into occupations late considered to be proper for men (Idam, 2020).

The female gender explicitly encounters gender segregation and discrimination in their professional prospects more than men as women procure around 30% of the general gender pay hole in low-paying businesses and the extent of male employees is more than 80% in better-paid enterprises which is unarguably high (Idam, 2020). Women additionally spend fewer hours on paid positions but spend longer on neglected positions. This shows that women have more work hours out each week than men and it could influence their professional decisions which is the reason the European Union advances more equivalent sharing of parental leaves and other adaptable courses of action (Rubery, 2015). Thus, women's activists have advanced the change of the controlled compensation economy in a setting in which those upholding genius progressive change has had little command over the political cycles, consequently unintentionally giving authenticity to the neoliberal reason (Rubery, 2015).

A portion of the issues faced by the female gender is the way that they have fewer open doors in possessing positions and advancement openings, maternity leaves restricting their advancement, paid less compensation in their movements, lewd behavior, and generalizations that place them to be more fragile than men, less uniformity business openings laws (Idam, 2020). Furthermore, an ordinary perception that they will end up being less useful after bringing forth youngsters and they would give less thought to their expected set of responsibilities. An expansive conviction recommends that women were not generally so capable as men, either in terms of physical ability or mental capacity or emotional stability. Women's maternity leaves are seen as deficiencies towards their professional improvement and attaining an administrative position; an enormous part of the women feel that commitments to the family impede their special way.

Gender diverse workforce could help with accomplishing the requirements and inclinations of male and female clients which summarizes an upper hand as every individual's capacity could be considered uncommon. a gender diverse workplace can show its vision with a wide scope of encounters, thoughts, and conclusions contrasted with a homogenous gathering. According to Eagly et al. (2003), gender diversity has emphatically affected businesses by encouraging inclusivity and headed creative drives in the workplace. Having a female workforce just as a male workforce in the team can accomplish a responsive climate as females are known for their exceptional attributes of being caring, kind, sensitive, sympathetic and thoughtful.

Having female and male employees is a benefit to the organization as a result of their distinction in moral thinking. Female employees are socially disposed and anxious to react to the necessities of others while male workers are centered on sticking to equity. Consolidating these capacities would accomplish authoritative objectives and develop worker commitment. A

gender-diverse workforce force would empower a decent equivalent conveyance of decision making in viewpoints that would lean toward all gatherings, albeit, this can too build struggle, decrease inspiration and worker commitment as certain representatives may not remain for certain chosen choices (Gilligan, 2014).

III. Ethnicity

According to Obi (2001), ethnicity is described as a distinctive characteristic among the internal dimension of diversity among employees in the workplace as related to multinational cooperation in an African context. Ahmad and Rahman (2019) describe ethnicity as a tribal gathering appreciating the similar history of the beginning and fostering a feeling of common fate. Diversity is centered on various social characters which incorporate gender, ethnicity, nationality, and religion and structure the way of life of an explicit group. Obi (2001) contends that recognizable contrasts of ethnicity in African organizations are the most critical in ensuring that the most capable and able people are utilized inside the labor force. According to Flanagan (2020), cultural diversity is any differentiation in people dictated by their experience, background, nationality, and tribe. The cultural condition in the organization portrays the current economic, social and cultural differences on a social level. For an organization to manage culturally unique employees, it would require profound agreement and the executives of frameworks to construct a useful result.

Juvonen et al. (2006) recognize ethnicity as a probable impacting factor for the accomplishment of any organization. This could be because it is a crucial classification of social personality that characterizes society and also fill in as a primary impact as well as a connecting factor among the inward components of employee diversity in accomplishing hierarchical putout objectives and goals. When the management practices are in synchrony with the ethnic diversity, the organization gain the upper hand from a successfully adjusted outer climate and inside design and the inability to do such will adversely affect the sustainability of the business. The more extensive the ethnic difference, the more costs association the worldwide will bring about consequently prompting decreased execution (Rodrigo et al., 2016). The distinctions in nationality can be brought imaginative and inventive execution among the individuals (Ahmad & Rahman, 2019).

It very well may be construed from the examination proof and attestations that viability and effectiveness in multicultural associations are a component of assorted abilities and inventiveness which come from more cooperation among individuals of various identities, ages, actual capacity, races and different traits. These characteristics should be well managed in an organization from the superior to subordinate in the organization for compelling and effective execution of performance and a sustainable business (Dewua, 2019).

Sustainability is “meeting the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs” (WCED, 1987, p.43). According to Svensson et al., (2016), this definition is the only one that breathes aggressive and proactive elements of sustainable development for the long-term well-being of the earth. Another meaning of sustainability can be seen from the three-dimensional phenomenon often refers to as triple-

bottom-line; these dimensions are, Social, Environmental and Economic. Sustainability is a principal normal for a dynamic, advancing system, Vicente et al., (2015) see sustainability as the company's capability and strategic management to successfully plan for future business, market, and operating environments. According to Bansal and DesJardine (2014), sustainability intends to get intergenerational value.

Every organization's obligation is often seen as sustainability, and it also provides a chance for the organization's growth and development. (Ferro et al., 2019). The triple bottom line theory states that to be sustainable and competitive, an organization must achieve a balance between its economic, environmental, and social bottom lines. (Cagnin et al., 2013). One of the simplest definitions of sustainability is that it is concerned with the impact that current actions have on the future possibilities available. In other words, a firm cannot be deemed sustainable if it uses resources in the present to the detriment of its ability to use resources in the future especially when those resources are finite.

Multinational Corporations' Sustainability

Sustainability according to Sen, (2021) is satisfying the needs of a firm's immediate and indirect stakeholders (such as shareholders, workers, clients, pressure groups, communities, and so on) without jeopardizing the firm's ability to satisfy the needs of future stakeholders as well. Also, Wagner et al (2014) sustainability is defined as an organization's effort to focus not just on profit but also on how to efficiently and effectively manage and absorb its environmental, social, and economic impacts. Sustainability entails an organization's attempts to manage and deal with its effect on the ecosystem and the entire business operation. Bansal and DesJardine, (2014) opined that sustainability is the capacity of firms to react to their momentary monetary necessities without undermining their (or others') capacity to meet their future requirements, however, the triple bottom line concern avows that an organization needs to arrive at equilibrium among its financial, environmental and social main concerns to be sustainable (Cagnin et al. 2013).

According to Ifeoma et al. (2019), the environment in which an MNCs operates has a significant impact on it, and any organization that wants to achieve and realize its goals and objectives must be able to respond to that environment. The authors went on to say that the business environment can be thought of as a combination of all environmental conditions and impacts that are capable of influencing or affecting company activities. The social-political, cultural, and economic aspects that influence the life, development, and advancement of a business outfit or adventure are referred to as the business environment.

Sustainability is a collection of actions involving analysis and decision-making across all business processes, acquired through a comprehensive understanding of current and future changes. (Ifeoma et al. 2019). Thus, sustainability is cultivated through frequent practices that go past conformity within the market and the society at large, rather it envelops wide economic, social and environmental aspects. (Wagner et al. 2014). Business sustainability is concerned with ensuring that the business does not grow out of assets, both human and technical materials, that are required for it to thrive. This also suggests that it does not merely look at a profit in the

short term, but instead runs in such a way that it is profitable and productive now and will be successful and productive in the future as well because it is properly utilizing all resources. (Ifeoma et al. 2019).

Theoretical Review

Social Identity Theory (SIT)

SIT was proposed by Henri Tajfel (1978). The theory places its theoretical significance on a complex and dynamic self that arbitrates the connection between social structure and individual conduct (Hogg et al., 1995). The author centred his agreement on the premise that people characterized their personalities concerning social groups, this social group helps to secure and reinforce the character and identity of individuals. A social identity is an individual awareness that they belong to a particular social group. Stets and Burke (2000) consider a social group to be a variety of people with the same social identification who see themselves as members of the same social family, Tajfel and Turner (2004) also describe a group as a collection of persons who believe in themselves to be members of the same social category, share some emotional connection, and establish some degree of social consensus regarding their group's and membership's appraisal.

According to Islam (2013), the formation of group identity includes two classifications which are “in-group” and “out-group”, it also involves the propensity to see one immediate group with an optimistic inclination opposite the other group which is the out-group. The fundamental proposition for SIT is that there is a social categorization which could be in form of nationality, ethnic groups, political party, sports team etc., which an individual fall and have a feeling of belongingness in that group. These social groups essentially help to shape a diverse other behavior, especially intergroup behavior. These social characteristics present self-improvement, add to self-conceptualization and increase confidence in individuals and their social status (Biomass et al., 2003).

SIT recommends that individuals get value as a result of their membership in a group utilizing notable characteristics and qualities. Individuals are motivated to acquire, and maintain a feeling of positive group dissimilarity from another group to which they do not belong and discriminate against in respect to their group. The theory believes that a person's conduct is largely affected by the personal relationship with a larger societal group and association to such an extent that the identification drives the inner cycles. SIT is with the view that people categorize themselves into distinguished groups depending on special and remarkable qualities and they act concerning their classification and settings that insist on group identity. It is also worthy to note that SIT makes emphasizes on both similarities and dissimilarities can promote grouping which thus promotes leaning towards favoring in-group at the inconvenience of other out-group. The in-group is made when people are dependent on the distinction that individuals recognize among themselves as well as other people within the organization or society. Self-classification will prompt separation and segregation which comes with a comparison with the social groups to which members belong (in-group) and any other remaining groups (out-group).

The position of this theory concerning workplace diversity and business sustainability is that all dimensions of diversity can result in either a positive or a negative outcome (Dewua, 2019). People with diverse dissimilarities are less likely to participate with others, while those with similarities will participate and collaborate towards achieving a common objective. The world of work is becoming more diverse than ever due to the influence of globalization which has made the world a global village (Inegbedion et al., 2020). Different and diverse individuals come together in the workplace for work, these individuals will probably respond to intragroup conflict as diversity in the organization is increment among the group, thus conflict is probably going to increase which would in turn cause issues and setbacks to the organizational goals and objectives. SIT aids the understanding and comprehension of elements that drive conflict within the group, favoritism, and discrimination in the workplace (Dewua, 2019). The theory further explains how individuals respond whenever they see their status to be inferior or when their participation with the group damages or affects their self-esteem and also clarifies the reasoning behind employees' social conduct within an organization as it relates between intergroup relations and numerous social peculiarities that underline the attachment and connection among individuals from a group, cooperative activities and individuals' aggregate conduct in an organization.

Empirical Review

The relationship between workplace diversity, workforce inclusion, and sustainability has been researched from various angles. It is then necessary to review some related studies conducted by various researchers in this field.

Inegbedion et al (2020) investigated "managing diversity for organizational effectiveness" at nine multinational corporations in southern Nigeria. Its purpose was to determine how much diversity management influences organizational efficiency through dispute resolution, cultural diversity, and employees' feelings of marginalization, collaboration, and work attitude. A survey design was adopted, and data were obtained from 178 respondents from nine multinational corporations in the south-south region. The results show that cultural diversity management, employee views of marginalization, and conflict all have a significant influence on diversity management. Furthermore, the management of collaboration and diversity has a significant influence on organizational efficiency. It was advised, among other things, that managers of diverse workforces should prioritize diversity management to assure its successful implementation.

In recent reviews, Tamunomiebi and John-Eke (2020) looked at emerging workplace diversity challenges. Given the demographic differences in employee ages, genders, races, ethnicities, cultures, and so on that typically drive productivity and business performance, globalization and trade liberalization, which allow productive factor inputs to freely move across countries, are largely driving such diversity or heterogeneous work organizations. According to the findings, workforce diversity has several benefits, including the creation of a learning-at-work environment through collaboration and team engagement, as well as increased productivity and profit. New challenges in workforce diversity, such as multicultural task contexts, the

availability of a diverse talent pool for creativity and innovation, cross coordination, complexity, and workplace discrimination, must be emphasized.

Oyedele et al (2018) investigated workforce diversity management strategies and organizational performance in the Food and Beverage Industries in Lagos State, Nigeria. The research focused on managing workforce diversity. The study evaluated three multinational corporations in the Nigerian food and beverage industry using a cross-sectional research approach and a random sample technique. The availability of talent, according to the study's findings, has a significant impact on employee retention. Diverse work teams add significant value to businesses, and workers benefit from embracing individual differences by gaining a competitive advantage and increase productivity. According to the findings, organizations should prioritize improving the diversity of their workforce. Organizations should make workforce diversity management a fundamental business value since diverse work teams bring considerable value to firms, and embracing individual differences benefits workers by providing a competitive edge and increasing productivity.

Akinnusi et al (2017) looked into how to foster effective workforce diversity management in Nigerian businesses: The challenge of human resource management in Nigeria, based on previous research, to provide a conceptual understanding and relevance of diversity, especially in the workplace. Human resource management (HRM) is inextricably linked to the social, economic, political, and legal contexts of a country. Nigeria is an appealing market for multinational firms from all over the world, with a population of over 180 million people, nearly half of whom are of working age. The workforce diversity of the nation's enterprises, both commercial and public, small and large, according to the findings, is a true wellspring of ideas, creativity, innovation, and vitality that can be mined indefinitely. To break free from the economic doldrums it is currently experiencing, Nigeria should look to its organizations to harness the synergy and creativity inherent in its diverse workforce

Ravazzani (2016) investigated understanding approaches for managing diversity in the workplace: An Empirical Investigation in Italy, The purpose of this research is to better understand why and how businesses adopt diversity management in practice, as well as the factors that may impact their decision. The study extends on current categorizations reflecting organizational-wide perspectives on diversity management by incorporating practice-driven indicators and identifying potential confounding factors. The resulting paradigm is being used to study diversity management in Italy. The findings of a 90-business survey and two focus sessions with experts and managers are provided. According to the findings, the most common strategy among Italian enterprises is based on social expectations, which appear to be produced by isomorphic pressures and the need to establish legitimacy in their surroundings. The findings propose a theory and practice of diversity management in Italy that incorporates compliance and opportunity-oriented aspects in the interplay between compulsion and voluntarism that represents local perspectives and aspirations.

Odita and Egbule (2015) examined workforce diversity and organizational effectiveness in the Nigerian brewing industry were researched to determine the effects of workforce diversity on brewing industry effectiveness utilizing selected Nigerian breweries. To choose respondents,

they used a survey design and stratified random sampling. Linear regression and correlation were used to examine the data gathered. They discovered a positive association between workforce diversity and organizational effectiveness, which was statistically significant. Cultural diversity was discovered to be more productive, and team building and group training were discovered to buffer the relationship between worker diversity and organizational effectiveness.

Method

The population of the study consisted of manufacturing multinational corporation operating in Nigeria. The population consisted of the industry's top, middle, and lower cadres of permanent employees, with the belief that all cadres are impacted or aware of diversity in some way. The sample size consisted of 375 employees of the selected MNCs. The study instrument was a structured questionnaire. The instrument contained Likert-type scale items. Cronbach's alpha was used to assess the instrument's reliability.

This study adopted a descriptive survey research design. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyze the data in the study. Regression analysis was performed to determine the internal dimensions of workplace diversity and sustainability in selected multinational corporations in Nigeria. The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) IBM version 26.0 was used to assess or discover the association between workforce diversity management and organizational success. Tables were used to present the data to provide a clear image of the study findings at a glance. The hypotheses were analyzed using regression analysis

Result and Discussion

The first item on Internal dimension, item one (ID1) had a mean score of 4.24 and a standard deviation of .627, item 2 (ID2) had a mean of 3.44 and standard deviation of 1.12, item 3 (ID3) had a mean of 3.62 and standard deviation of 1.2, item 4 (ID4) had a mean of 4.20 and standard deviation of .587, item 5 (ID5) had a mean of 4.28 and standard deviation of .70. From table 4.4 the grand mean of 3.95 indicates that the responses tilted toward agreement. The standard deviation of .85 indicates that the responses are slightly and relatively varied

H₀₁: Internal dimensions of workplace diversity do not significantly contribute to the sustainability of selected manufacturing multinational corporations. Table 1 (see appendix 1), shows that internal dimensions have a significant impact on the sustainability of selected manufacturing MNCs in Nigeria at a 5% level of significance ($\beta = -.192$, $t = 3.119$ $p = .002$). This means that internal dimensions have a significant relationship with the sustainability of selected manufacturing MNCs in Nigeria. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted and the alternate hypothesis rejected. The result of the hypothesis implies that MNCs with a wide range of employees with diverse internal dimensions (age, gender, race) have high sustainability.

Discussion of findings

The hypothesis tests whether internal dimensions of workplace diversity had a significant relationship with the sustainability of manufacturing MNC operating in Nigeria. According to the findings of this study, there is a significant positive relationship between internal workplace diversity dimensions and sustainability with a beta coefficient score of .192. This implies that for every 1 unit increase in the internal dimension, sustainability is positively affected by .192units. Hence, the hypothesis which stated that Internal dimensions do not significantly contribute to the sustainability of selected manufacturing multinational corporations is rejected.

This finding is similar to the works of Kundu and Mor, (2016), (Kundu and Mor, (2017), Joseph and Selvaraj, (2015) and Dewua, (2019) who believe that the internal dimension of workplace diversity can lead to an innovative and creative performance in an organization by broadening the viewpoints and perspectives of the individuals involved.

The findings imply that organizations that embrace employees with diverse internal dimensions have diverse approaches to problem-solving, which will improve the organization's productivity. The more people from diverse backgrounds there are in the workforce, the more diverse and prosperous it is. When people from diverse backgrounds are hired, there is a good chance that they will contribute to the organization's productivity. Aligning the pool of experience and knowledge among employees with diverse ethnic backgrounds, ages, and gender fosters innovation and creativity, allowing the organization to be productive in terms of performance and increased products.

Conclusion

Workplace diversity is unavoidable in Nigerian manufacturing MNCs because most workers have different social and economic statuses, which induces their actions or thinking to differ from others, which must be managed for the organization to be effective. When managed properly, the organization will interact with people from various cultures, ethnic groups, age race, gender and also diverse customers, which will aid in the development of new attitudes, ideas, skills, processes, and solutions to difficult problems. It will also improve the organizations' adaptability to market knowledge, customer and society loyalty, innovative thinking, and employee attraction and retention. According to the findings, diverse internal dimensions (age, gender, race) have a positive relationship with sustainability (environmental, economic, and social) of manufacturing MNCs in Nigeria. Organizations are made up of people of various races, ages and gender. Organizations must recognize differences and learn to use them to their advantage to be effective, as ignoring or allowing differences may cause problems in achieving the organization's set goals. Encouragement and management of internal dimension of diversity in an organization lead to increased business and sustainability. This is because bringing employees from various backgrounds, different age groups, and gender into an organization enables them to share their belief systems, skills, and knowledge, which aids in problem-solving. A more diverse pool of skills and knowledge based on mixed internal dimensions of workplace diversity fosters creativity and innovation, which can provide a competitive advantage for the organization while also increasing sustainability.

Recommendations

Manufacturing MNCs in Nigeria should intentionally establish teams comprised of employees with varying internal dimensions (age, race, gender). Organizations should recruit across a wider geographic region so that more potential candidates can get job opportunities to demonstrate their abilities. This will result in a pool of skills, knowledge, and experience for the organization's creativity and innovation. Diversity should be viewed as a means or tool for organizational effectiveness workplace diversity should be woven into the fabrics and DNA of the organizations. which will promote the organization to fund programmes or activities involved in managing workplace diversity for organizational sustainability.

Acknowledgments

Our sincere appreciation goes to everyone who have contributed to the success of this work.

Declaration of interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

References

- Afolabi, A., & Laseinde, O. T. (2019). Manufacturing Sector Performance and Economic Growth in Nigeria. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1378(3). <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1378/3/032067>
- Ahmad, S., & Rahman, F. U. (2019). Effect of Workplace Diversity on Employees ' Performance in Allama Iqbal Open University. *Pakistan Journal of Distance Learning*, 5(2), 85–100.
- Akinnusi, D. M., Sonubi, O. O., & Oyewunmi, A. E. (2017). Fostering effective workforce diversity management in Nigerian organizations: the challenge of human resource management. *International Review of Management and Marketing*, 7(2), 108–116.
- Amos, A., & Uniamikogbo, E. (2016). Sustainability and Triple Bottom Line : an Overview of Two Interrelated Concepts. *Igbinedion University Journal of Accounting*, 2(August), 88–126.
- Anekwe, R. I., Ndubusi-Okolo, P., & Chuka, U. (2019). Sustainability in the Nigerian business environment : problems and prospects. *International Journal of Academic Management Science Research (IJAMSR)*, 3(3), 72–80.
- Banjoko, S. A., Iwuji, I. I., & Bagshaw, K. (2012). The performance of the Nigerian manufacturing sector: A 52-Year analysis of growth and retrogression. *Asian Economic and Social Society*, 2(8), 177–191.
- Bansal, P., & DesJardine, M. (2014). Business sustainability: It is about time. *Strategic Organization*, 12(1), 70–78. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1476127013520265>
- Betchoo, N. K. (2015). *Managing Workplace Diversity*.
- Biomass, B. F., Gide, A., Structures, M. B., Liliani, D. E., & Hum, M. (2003). Identity, Social Identity, Comparison, and Status: Four Theories with a Common Core. *Angewandte Chemie International Edition*, 6(11), 951–952., 52(1), 5–24.
- Boni-Saenz, A. A. (2021). Age Diversity. *Southern California Law Review*, 94, 303–355.
- Cagnin, C. H., Loveridge, D., & Butler, J. (2013). Business Sustainability Maturity Model. In PREST, Institute

of Innovation of the University of Manchester, UK.

Cedric, H. (2009). Does Diversity Pay?: Race, Gender, and the Business Case for Diversity. *American Sociological Review*, 74(2), 208–224.

Chin, J. L., & Trimble, J. E. (2020). Dimensions of Diversity. In *Diversity and Leadership* (pp. 21–52). <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781483368801.n4>

Dewua, P. (2019). Workforce Diversity Management and Organizational Effectiveness in the Nigerian Petroleum Industry.

Durst, S., & Zieba, M. (2020). Knowledge risks inherent in business sustainability. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 251, 119670. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.119670>

Eagly, A. H., Johannesen-Schmidt, M. C., & Van Engen, M. L. (2003). Transformational, Transactional, and Laissez-Faire Leadership Styles: A Meta-Analysis Comparing Women and Men. *Psychological Bulletin*, 129(4), 569–591. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-2909.129.4.569>

Ellemers, N., van Knippenberg, A., De Vries, N., & Wilke, H. (1988). Social identification and permeability of group boundaries. *European Journal of Social Psychology*, 18(6), 497–513. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ejsp.2420180604>

Ferro, C., Padin, C., Høgevold, N., Svensson, G., & Sosa Varela, J. C. (2019). Validating and expanding a framework of a triple bottom line dominant logic for business sustainability through time and across contexts. *Journal of Business and Industrial Marketing*, 34(1), 95–116. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JBIM-07-2017-0181>

Gilligan, C. (2014). In a different voice: Women’s conceptions of self and morality. *Feminist Social Thought: A Reader*, 47(4), 549–582. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203705841-42>

Hall, J. (2011). Diversity in the Workplace: The Journey. *The Dynamics of Managing Diversity*, 97–126. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315767147-10>

Harrison, D. A., Gavin, J. H., & Florey, A. T. (2002). Time, Teams, and Task Performance : Changing Effects of Surface- and Deep-Level Diversity on Group Functioning. *Academy of Management Journal*, 45(5), 1029–1045.

Hogg, M. a., Terry, D. J., & White, K. M. (1995). A Tale of Two Theories : A Critical Comparison of Identity Theory with Social Identity Theory. *Social Psychology Quarterly*, 58(4), 255–269.

Idam, C. A. (2020). The role of diversity in influencing employee Engagement in multinational corporations in Nigeria (Issue August).

Ifeoma, A. R., Purity, N., & Chuka, U. (2019). Sustainability in the Nigerian Business Environment : Problems and Prospects. *International Journal of Academic Management Science Research*, 3(3), 72–80.

Inegbedion, H., Sunday, E., Asaley, A., Lawal, A., & Adebajji, A. (2020). Managing diversity for organizational efficiency. *SAGE Open*, 10(1), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244019900173>

Islam, G. (2013). Social identity theory. *Institute for Education and Research, Grenoble, France*, 2014, 255–272. <https://doi.org/10.5840/iabsproc19967101>

Joseph, D., & Selvaraj, palanisamy C. (2015). The effects of work Force diversity on employee performance in Singapore organisations. *International Journal of Business Administration*, 6(2), 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.5430/ijba.v6n2p17>

Joseph, O., Solomon, O., Gabriel, O. O. C., & Eluka, J. (2019). Environmental management practices and sustainability of multinational companies in South-South, Nigeria. *Journal of Business and Retail Management Research (JBRMR)*, 13(3), 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.24052/JBRMR/V13IS03/ART-16>

Juvonen, J., Nishina, A., & Graham, S. (2006). Ethnic diversity and perceptions of safety in urban middle schools. *Psychological Science*, 17(5), 393–400. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9280.2006.01718.x>

- Kanza, T. K., & Shaista, J. (2019). Investigating the impact of workplace diversity on organizational citizenship behaviour: the mediating role of inclusion. *Journal of Management and Research*, 6(2), 18–50. <https://doi.org/10.29145/jmr/62/060202>
- Kundu, S. C., & Mor, A. (2016). Effect of Diversity Management on Employees Organisational Commitment: A Study of Indian Organisations. *Journal of Strategic Human Resource Management*, 5(1). <https://doi.org/10.21863/jshrm/2016.5.1.021>
- Kundu, S., & Mor, A. (2017). Workforce diversity and organizational performance: a study of IT industry in India. Emerald Publishing Limited, 39(2), 160–183. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ER-06-2015-0114>
- Mensah, J. (2019). Sustainable development: Meaning, history, principles, pillars, and implications for human action: Literature review. *Cogent Social Sciences*, 5(1), 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311886.2019.1653531>
- Muthoni, M. D. (2017). Workforce Diversity Management and Employee Performance in National Biosafety Authority, Kenya.
- Obi, Cyril I. (2001). The Changing Forms of Identity Politics in Nigeria Under Economic Adjustment: The Case of the Oil Minorities Movement of the Niger Delta. *Africa Today*, 49(1), 108–110. <https://doi.org/10.1353/at.2002.0005>
- Odita, A. O., & Egbule, S. (2015). Workforce Diversity and Organizational Effectiveness in Nigerian Brewery Industry. Undefined.
- Oyati, E. (2010). The Relevance, Prospects and the Challenges of the Manufacturing Sector in Nigeria (pp. 1–12).
- Oyedele, O. O., Issa, A., & Brimah, A. N. (2018). Workforce diversity management strategies and organizational performance in the food and beverage industries in Lagos State, Nigeria. *Scholes International Journal of Management*, 05(01), 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.19085/journal.sijmd050101>
- Preeti, B., Poonam, L., & Ekanshi, G. (2014). Workforce Diversity Management: Biggest Challenge Or Opportunity For 21st Century Organizations Gupta; *Journal of Business and Management*, 16(4), 102–107.
- Ravazzani, S. (2016). Understanding approaches for managing diversity in the workplace: An empirical investigation in Italy. *Equality, Diversity and Inclusion*, 35(2), 154–168. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EDI-08-2014-0062>
- Rodrigo, V., Romeo, V., Rowena, L., & Venus, V. (2016). Diversity in the workplace: Evidence from gulf college, Oman. *Journal of Asian Business Strategy*, 6(4), 73–84. <https://doi.org/10.18488/journal.1006/2016.6.4/1006.4.73.84>
- Rubery, J. (2015). Austerity and the future for gender equality in Europe. *Industrial and Labor Relations Review*, 68(4), 715–741. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0019793915588892>
- Sen, Y. (2021). Essentials of Sustainability: A Roadmap for Businesses. In *Sustainable Management for Managers and Engineers* (pp. 67–88). <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119804345.ch4>
- Stets, J. E., & Burke, P. J. (2000). Identity theory and social identity theory. *Social Psychology Quarterly*, 63(3), 224–237. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2695870>
- Svensson, G., Padin, C., & Eriksson, D. (2016). Glocal business sustainability - performance beyond zero! *International Journal of Procurement Management*, 9(1), 15–26. <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJPM.2016.073385>
- Szymanska, A., & Aldighieri, D. (2017). Diversity and inclusion in the workplace: employee perception and implications for internal brand management. *International Conference on Advances in Business, Management and Law (ICABML) 2017*, 1(1), 368–388. <https://doi.org/10.30585/icabml-cp.v1i1.32>
- Tajfel, H. (1978). Experiments in Intergroup Discrimination. *Scientific American*, 223, 96–102.
- Tajfel, H., & Turner, J. C. (2004). The Social Identity Theory of Intergroup Behaviour. In *The Social Identity*

Theory of Intergroup Behavior.

Tamunomiebi, M. D., & John-Eke, E. C. (2020). Workplace diversity: emerging issues in contemporary reviews. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business & Social Sciences*, 10(2), 255–265. <https://doi.org/10.6007/IJARBSS/v10-i2/6926>

Vicente, S., Alves, A. C., Carvalho, M. S., & Costa, N. (2015). Business sustainability through employees involvement: A case study. *FME Transactions*, 43(4), 362–369. <https://doi.org/10.5937/fmet1504362V>

Wagner, B., Ferro, C., Varela, J. C., & Høgevoold, N. M. (2014). Sustainable business models: Corporate reasons, economic effects, social boundaries, environmental actions and organizational challenges in sustainable business practices. *Baltic Journal of Management*, 9(3), 357–380. <https://doi.org/10.1108/BJM-09-2013-0147>

WCED. (1987). Report of the world commission on environment and development: our common future (Vol. 4, Issue 1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/07488008808408783>

Tables.

The tables below show the result of findings of the study

Table 1: Internal Dimensions

Items	SA (%)	A (%)	N (%)	D (%)	SD (%)	M	SDV
ID1	85(33.3)	147(57.6)	-	21(8.2)	2(.8)	4.24	.627
ID2	46(18)	89(34.9)	16(6.3)	36(14.1)	68(26.7)	3.44	1.12
ID3	61(23.9)	99(38.8)	16(6.3)	47(18.4)	32(12.5)	3.62	1.2
ID4	75(29.4)	157(61.6)	-	23()	-	4.20	.587
ID5	102(40)	128(50.2)	-	19(7.5)	6(2.4)	4.28	.70
Grand Mean						3.95	.85

Source: SPSS Output, Field survey (2022)

Table 2: Sustainability

Items	VH (%)	H (%)	A (%)	L (%)	VL (%)	M	SDV
Social							
SS1	102(40)	124(48.6)	28(11)	1(0.4)		4.28	.669
SS2	79(31)	141(55.3)	32(12.5)	3(1.2)	-	4.16	.677
SS3	108(42.4)	101(39.6)	45(17.6)	1(0.4)	-	4.24	.749
SS4	120(47.1)	92(36.1)	38(14.9)	5(2.0)		4.28	.788
Grand Mean						4.24	.72
Economic							
ES1	108(42.4)	101(39.6)	43(16.9)	3(1.2)		4.23	.767
ES2	95(37.3)	116(45.5)	41(16.1)	3(1.2)	-	4.19	.740
ES3	102(40)	97(38)	51(20)	5(2)		4.16	.809
ES4	106(41.6)	121(47.5)	26(10.2)	2(.8)		4.30	.680
Grand Mean						4.22	.749
Environmental							
EVS1	109(42.7)	75(29.4)	61(23.9)	10(3.9)		4.10	.902
EVS2	87(34.1)	112(43.9)	54(21.2)	2(.8)		4.11	.757
EVS3	101(39.6)	112(43.9)	41(16.1)	1(.4)		4.22	.723
EVS4	99(38.8)	114(44.7)	37(14.5)	5(2.0)		4.20	.756
Grand Mean						4.16	.78

Source: SPSS Output, Field survey (2022)

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics of variables

Variables	Min.	Max.	Mean	Std. Dev	Skewness		Kurtosis	
	Stat.	Stat.	Stat.	Stat.	Stat.	Std. Error	Stat.	Std. Error
Internal D	2.60	5.00	3.95	.50513	.009	.153	-.401	.304
Sustainability	2.50	5.00	4.20	.55133	-.712	.153	.021	.304

Source: SPSS Output, Field Survey (2022)